

**DEVELOPING AND EVALUATING PROMOTIONAL BROCHURES FOR
MASTER OF SCIENCE IN DEVELOPMENT COMMUNICATION: A PRETEST-
POSTTEST STUDY**

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ABSTRACT

Brochures have been one of the most effective tools used to inform, to educate and to communicate products, services and important information. This study aimed to develop a brochure that best promotes the Master of Science in Development Communication program of the University of Southeastern Philippines. The study used a nonrandomized control group pretest-posttest experimental design. There were thirty respondents chosen through purposive sampling. Adopted questionnaires for communication tool evaluation was the research instrument used in data gathering. Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test for dependent samples were the statistical tools used in the study. The brochure was evaluated in terms of identification, comprehension, clarity, acceptability, motivation, attractiveness, gender sensitivity and production quality. Based on the findings, pretesting and post testing improved the promotional brochure being developed for the Master of Science in Development Communication program. By focusing on the pretest results, it allowed the communication tool developers to successfully improve the effectiveness of the brochure. Moreover, modifications made based on the pretest results generally led to significant differences after the posttest. Only acceptability and gender sensitivity did not show any significant differences, as they were already high to very high during the pretest and they did not need much modification. Thus, an effective brochure for the Master of Science in Development Communication program was developed.

KEYWORDS:

Brochure, identification, comprehension, clarity, acceptability, motivation, attractiveness, gender sensitivity, production quality

INTRODUCTION

Brochures are one of the most effective and versatile tools used to inform, to educate and to communicate products, services and important information. Brochures are versatile as they are simple to produce, cost-effective and easy to distribute [1]. They are also effective as countless researches have showed that brochures were factors in either selling products or influencing behavior to and among people.

In 2005, Andreck developed tourist brochures for Glendale, Arizona and had them evaluated. The results of the mail survey suggested that the brochures significantly increase respondents' interest in visiting Glendale, Arizona [2]. In 2006, Denberg et al. evaluated the effectiveness of brochures in educating Colorado patients about screening colonoscopy, in addressing their fears and misconceptions about the procedure and in increasing the number of patients willing to go through with the procedure. Through a randomized controlled trial study among 781 patients, it was found out that overall adherence increased by 11.7%. It was then concluded that brochures were effective tools in increasing patient participation in screening colonoscopy [3].

In 2012, Saguin evaluated the effectiveness of the Citizen's Charter (which was also manifested in the form of brochures) in the Philippines. The study revealed that the brochures, posters, leaflets and booklets that contained the Citizen's Charter led to better informed citizens [4]. Less questions were asked and less complaints were received. Furthermore, it led to a reduction of complaints by 80%. In 1986, Durante et al. looked into IEC (Information, Education and Communication) materials for breastfeeding and its effect in select cities in Mindanao – Davao being one of them. Their study revealed that the IEC package, which contained leaflets and brochures, significantly increased Davaoña mothers' knowledge of breastfeeding [5]. Furthermore, attitudes towards breastfeeding significantly changed and incidence of breastfeeding was as high as 96% at birth after being exposed to the IEC materials.

These instances have shown that brochures are effective tools for promotion of products, knowledge and behavior. It is in this context that this study focused on the development of promotional brochures for the Master of Science in Development Communication program of the University of Southeastern Philippines.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Generally, the study aims to develop a promotional brochure for the Master of Science in Development Communication program of the University of Southeastern Philippines.

Moreover, the parameters being considered for an effective communication tool are identification, comprehension, clarity, acceptability, motivation, attractiveness, gender sensitivity and production quality, as described by the Ministry of Health, National AIDS Council, Malaria Control Centre and the Communications Support for Health [6].

Identification. Identification refers to the relevance and appropriateness of a communication tool to its intended audience. It tries to assess whether the intended audience can identify with the messages being conveyed by the communication tool.

Comprehension. Comprehension refers to the understandability of the communication tool. It tries to assess whether the messages in the communication tool is deemed comprehensible by the intended audience.

Clarity. Clarity does not refer to visual clarity, but whether the intended audience can simply grasp the information being conveyed through the messages and illustrations used.

Acceptability. Acceptability tries to assess whether the messages and illustrations used were acceptable or not to the intended audience. The communication tool should not alienate the members of its intended audience.

Motivation. Motivation refers to the ability of the communication tool to move its intended audience to act. It tries to assess whether the messages motivate the intended audience to do the desired action or not.

Attractiveness. Attractiveness refers to how interesting and engaging the communication tool is to the intended audience. It tries to assess whether the communication material is attractive and memorable and if it stands out to the intended audience.

Gender Sensitivity. Gender sensitivity addresses inequitable gender roles and stereotypes prevalent in the society. It tries to assess whether the messages and illustrations found in the communication tool are appropriate to the needs and circumstances of all genders.

Production Quality. Production quality has something to do with the quality of printing, the formatting and the layout of the communication tool. It also includes the use of logos and its size and necessity to the communication tool.

According to the Ministry of Health et al., testing communication tools using the provided criteria allows the communication tool developers to improve the material to ensure maximum impact on the intended audience. Significant differences will be made based on the results of the testing. Furthermore, testing ensures that the tools become more understandable, more acceptable and ready for reproduction [6].

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study was conducted to develop an effective brochure that best promotes the Master of Science in Development Communication program of the University of Southeastern Philippines. Moreover, this study evaluated the effectiveness of the brochure in terms of identification, comprehension, clarity, acceptability, motivation, attractiveness, gender sensitivity and production quality.

METHODOLOGY

The study used a nonrandomized control group pretest-posttest experimental design. Thirty respondents were chosen through purposive sampling. These respondents were chosen to represent individuals who are most

likely to pursue graduate studies. Adopted questionnaires for communication tools evaluation was the research instrument used in data gathering and was personally administered by the researchers to the respondents. Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test for dependent samples were the statistical tools used in the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section shows the analysis and interpretation of the gathered data.

Pretest and Posttest Evaluation of the Promotional Brochure for MS in Development Communication.

Disclosed in Table 1 is the pretest and posttest result on the evaluation of the promotional brochure for MS in Development Communication. In the pretest, the overall mean rating of the brochure is 4.00, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that overall, the brochure is generally very well done according to the respondents. In each criteria, the mean rating are as follows: identification with 4.13 (high), comprehension with 4.14 (high), clarity with 4.08 (high), acceptability with 4.27 (very high), motivation with 4.03 (high), attractiveness with 3.33 (moderate), gender sensitivity with 4.12 (high), and production quality with 3.91 (high). The pretest revealed that there are grounds for improvement in the brochure, especially for those criteria which were rated moderate and high by the respondents.

After the modifications were made, the posttest evaluation was held with the same respondents. In the posttest, the overall mean rating of the brochure is 4.74, with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that after the modifications were made, the brochure has become excellently done according to the respondents. Furthermore, the mean rating for the following criteria are as follows: identification with 4.72, comprehension with 4.85, clarity with 4.82, acceptability with 4.65, motivation with 4.64, attractiveness with 4.63, gender sensitivity with 4.67, and production quality with 4.94 – all of these with a descriptive level of very high. The posttest revealed that due to the modifications made in the key areas in the brochure that needed improvement, the brochure has become more effective as a promotional tool.

These findings coincide with the guidelines set by the Ministry of Health, National AIDS Council, Malaria Control Centre and the Communications Support for Health. Pretesting the brochure helped in the improvement of the material to ensure maximum impact on the intended audience, and also ensured that the brochure became more understandable, more acceptable and ready for reproduction [6]. Also, by evaluating the brochure using identification (relevance with the intended audience), comprehension (understandability of the messages), clarity (simplicity of the message), acceptability (acceptance of the message by the intended audience), motivation (the ability to move its intended audience to act), attractiveness (how interesting and engaging the communication tool is), gender sensitivity (appropriateness to all genders) and production quality as parameters, the effectiveness of the communication tool has been accounted for.

Table 1: Pretest and Posttest Evaluation of the Promotional Brochure for MS in Development Communication

	Pretest			Posttest		
	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Identification	.77	4.13	High	.35	4.72	Very High
Comprehension	.82	4.14	High	.23	4.85	Very High
Clarity	.86	4.08	High	.23	4.82	Very High
Acceptability	.78	4.27	Very High	.33	4.65	Very High
Motivation	.94	4.03	High	.40	4.64	Very High
Attractiveness	1.11	3.33	Moderate	.45	4.63	Very High
Gender Sensitivity	1.70	4.12	High	.38	4.67	Very High
Production Quality	.72	3.91	High	.10	4.94	Very High
Overall	.74	4.00	High	.23	4.74	Very High

Illustration 1: Promotional Brochure for MS in Development Communication Used for Pretesting

Illustration 2: Promotional Brochure for MS in Development Communication Used for Post Testing

Significant Difference in the Pretest and Posttest Evaluation of the Promotional Brochure for MS in Development Communication. Disclosed in Table 2 is the significant difference in the pretest and posttest evaluation of the promotional brochure for MS in Development Communication. Overall, the difference between the pretest and the posttest posted a t-value of 4.494 and a p-value of .000, less than .05 level of significance. This indicates that the null hypothesis should be rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis – there is a significant difference between the pretest results and posttest results. In each criteria, the t-value and p-value are as follows: identification with a t-value of 3.628 and a p-value of .002, comprehension with a t-value of 3.839 and a p-value of .001, clarity with a t-value of 3.679 and a p-value of .002, acceptability with a t-value of 2.063 and a p-value of .053, motivation with a t-value of 3.345 and a p-value of .003, attractiveness with a t-value of 4.760 and a p-value of .000, gender sensitivity with a t-value of 1.997 and a p-value of 0.060, and production quality with a t-value of 6.402 and a p-value of .000. From these values, this indicates that the null hypotheses for identification, comprehension, clarity, motivation, attractiveness and production quality should be rejected in favor of the alternative hypotheses – there were significant differences between the pretest results and posttest results of the brochures in these criteria. On the other hand, the t-values of acceptability and gender sensitivity are more than 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that the null hypotheses should be accepted in favor of the alternative hypothesis – there were no significant differences between the pretest and posttest results of the brochure in these criteria.

These findings coincide with the guidelines set by the Ministry of Health, National AIDS Council, Malaria Control Centre and the Communications Support for Health. Testing a communication tool for evaluation will reveal areas for improvement that the communication tool developers can work upon. Thus, more likely than not, there will be significant differences in the final form of the tool compared to its earlier form [6]. Though

acceptability and gender sensitivity did not show any significant differences, this was not considered as a negative as these were already high to very high during the pretest. These two criteria were the two areas where the brochure did not need much modification.

Table 2: Significant Difference in the Pretest and Posttest Evaluation of the Promotional Brochure for MS in Development Communication

	Pretest	Posttest	T-value	P-value	Decision on Ho
Identification	4.13	4.72	3.628	.002	Reject
Comprehension	4.14	4.85	3.839	.001	Reject
Clarity	4.08	4.82	3.679	.002	Reject
Acceptability	4.27	4.65	2.063	.053	Accept
Motivation	4.03	4.64	3.345	.003	Reject
Attractiveness	3.33	4.63	4.760	.000	Reject
Gender Sensitivity	4.12	4.67	1.997	.060	Accept
Production Quality	3.91	4.94	6.402	.000	Reject
Overall	4.00	4.74	4.494	.000	Reject

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the researchers concluded that pretesting and post testing improved the promotional brochure being developed for the Master of Science in Development Communication program. Pretesting results revealed the areas where the brochure needed improvements and modifications in terms of identification, comprehension, clarity, acceptability, motivation, attractiveness, gender sensitivity and production quality. By focusing on the pretest results, it allowed the communication tool developers to successfully improve the effectiveness of the brochure. Moreover, modifications made based on the pretest results generally led to significant differences after the posttest. Only acceptability and gender sensitivity did not show any significant differences, as they were already high to very high in during the pretest and did not need much modification. Thus, an effective brochure for the Master of Science in Development Communication program was developed.

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